

MANIFESTATION OF SPIRITUAL SELF AMONG STUDENTS IN A UNIVERSITY DURING PANDEMIC

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Manifestation of Spiritual Self among Students in a University During Pandemic

Lycel L. Pacheco, * Zarena V. Pacheco, Lovelyn J. Palata, Girlie M. Villanueva
For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

This research titled “Manifestation of Spiritual Self among Students in a University during Pandemic” was conducted to Bachelor of Arts in Social Science students enrolled during the school year 2022-2023. This is descriptive research which aimed to determine the manifestation of the spiritual self of AB Social Science students of Central Philippines State University during the pandemic. The self-made survey questionnaire was used to gather the data and used frequency and percentage, mean, standard deviation, Mann-Whitney and Kruskal Wallis Test in analyzing the data. Results revealed the spiritual-self manifestation among students was influenced by their year level. The higher their year level, the higher their views on the level of agreement. Furthermore, the respondents are strongly agreeing in the level of spiritual-self manifestation. The researchers concluded that the spiritual-self manifestation among students of Bachelor of Arts in Social Science at Central Philippines State University have a sense of connection to something higher than themselves. Valuing the meaning of their lives and the truth about the universe to cope up challenges in life, and experiences of well-being compassionately. Manifestation of students benefits literally every area of one’s life because it empowers to become the very best version of life that exists, embody every individual most want to become, and help to unlock the infinite potential reflections of life to create the purpose of it in this ever-changing world. Furthermore, ABSS students have a strong level of agreement which considered students responses clear thoughts in their spiritual well-being, they expose their abilities with purpose, harmony and great balance in whatever challenges they are facing.

Keywords: *manifestation, spiritual self, students, university, pandemic*

Introduction

In an analysis of a recent Indian study on COVID -19, the illness can make people anxious which can then lead to psychological abnormalities like post-traumatic stress disorder and other behavioral disorders. Early manifestations of COVID -19 have aroused concern about contracting it. Due to the illness’s fatal prognosis, the populace is beginning to experience emotional and psychological distress (SOOD, 2020). The author argues that while there will undoubtedly be a wide range of negative effects during this international crisis, some good behavioral results may also be anticipated. A theory in social behavioral holds that when confronted with terrifying circumstances, a person’s cognitive abilities cause them to become aware that death is unavoidable and could happen at any time. Such self-awareness inspires people to comprehend their life philosophy in great detail, which improves their spiritual outlook and even transforms the profane into the sacred. Additionally, it is thought that those who have the capacity to access higher states of spiritual consciousness may experience spiritual transformation that results from self-awareness with a relative intensity that is higher.

Recent events, particularly the impact of COVID-19 on our spirituality, have heightened our sense of urgency in addressing the role of spirituality in our lives. Pastors, chaplains, and religious leaders are also seen as spiritual front runners in the fight against COVID-19. Through their selfless service such as consultation, spiritual direction, discussion programs, anointing of the sick, hearing confession, and palliative intervention they have provided love, care, and compassion to those who are experiencing trauma, grief, stress, depression, and anxiety. She believe that now, more than ever, they must take the role of spirituality seriously, not only in critical moments in our history, but also in everyday life. Faced with such a pervasive, upsetting event that caused daily fragility, fear, and uncertainty during the COVID-19 pandemic, the AB Social Science students manifested their spiritual selves. In particular, the spiritual distress of AB Social Science students going through challenging circumstances, like that brought on by COVID-19, should not be underestimated. The spiritual side of their existence keeps them sane and hopeful that something positive will happen, despite the risk of contracting this sickness in huge groups.

These facts inspired the researchers to determine the manifestation of the spiritual self of AB Social Science Students of Central Philippine State University during the pandemic.

Research Objectives

The main objective of this study is to assess the manifestation of spiritual self among students of Central Philippines State University during pandemic. Specifically, this study determined the profile of the respondents in terms of age, sex, year level and monthly family income, the level of agreement of the AB Social Science Students’ manifestation of spiritual self during pandemic and the difference between the level of agreement for the manifestation of spiritual self of AB Social Science students when grouped according to profile.

Methodology

This section presents the research design, the respondents of study, sampling techniques, data collection instruments and procedure and data analysis.

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive research design to determine the extent of manifestation of spiritual self of the students during pandemic to attain the aims and purposes of this study.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the Bachelor of Arts in Social Science Students of Central Philippines State University. The target population of officially enrolled students during the 1st semester academic year 2022-2023 is 265, out of this population, a sample of 162 served as the actual respondents who actively take part in the content of the survey.

Instrument

A self-made survey questionnaire was used to gather data on the manifestation of spiritual self among students of Central Philippines State University during pandemic which was triangulated with personal interviews and focused group discussions being conducted.

Procedure

Data on the manifestation of spiritual self among students of Central Philippines State University during pandemic were gathered through a self-made survey questionnaire which the researchers personally administered to the respondents. Interviews and discussions were conducted to selected respondents to gather additional information in relation to the way they manifest their spirituality in times of crisis like the pandemic.

Prior to analysis, the researchers examined the data for duplication of responses. Data cleaning and editing was done to ensure the data is of quality and ready for statistical analysis.

Data Analysis

Appropriate statistical tools were used to answer the given research problems. Frequency counts and percentage distributions were used to determine the profile of the respondents in terms of gender. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to determine the level of agreement of the AB Social Science Students' manifestation of spiritual self during pandemic Kruskal -Wallis Test was used to determine the difference between the level of agreement for the manifestation of spiritual self of AB Social Science students when grouped according to profile.

Results and Discussion

This section deals with the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of data. Results are presented in tables followed by descriptive analyses and statistical interpretation. Implications of the findings are also given with the support from relevant studies and future research.

Respondent's Demographic Profile

Table 1. *Profile of the Respondents as to age, sex, year level and family monthly income*

<i>Variable</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
Age		
18 - 19	23	14.20 %
20 - 21	69	42.59 %
22 - 24	58	35.80 %
25 - 30	12	7.41 %
Sex		
Male	43	26.54 %
Female	119	73.46 %
Year Level		
1st Year	35	21.60%
2nd Year	48	29.63 %
3rd Year	36	22.22%
4th Year	43	26.54 %
Family Monthly Income		
Below 10k	110	67.90%
10k - 15k	44	27.16 %
Above 15k	8	4.94%
Total	162	100

Result shows the demographic profile of the ABSS students as to age, sex, year level and monthly family income. As to age, 69 of the ABSS students were aging 20-21 which is 42.59% of the total respondents while the lowest number or 12 ABSS students were those aging 25-30 with a percentage of 7.41. This implies that the majority of the ABSS students were viewed as being of an age appropriate

for college and most of them are female.

Most of the respondents were second year in which as to family income, the highest number of them are earning less than P10,000 and only a few has a family income of P15,000 per month. This implies that most of the ABSS students came from poor family with very low monthly earnings.

Students Level of Agreement in Terms of Spiritual Self Manifestation

Table 2. How students agree in terms of spiritual self manifestation (n = 162)

<i>Spiritual Self Manifestation</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>SD</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
I have no doubt that God exists	4.83	0.467	Strongly Agree
God knows when I need him	4.85	0.411	Strongly Agree
I feel God is responsible to when I pray enough	4.67	0.630	Strongly Agree
When good or bad things happen, I believe those are part of God's plans	4.72	0.537	Strongly Agree
What my life has to accomplish is already decided by God	4.64	0.627	Strongly Agree
I believe in God at all cost	4.79	0.452	Strongly Agree
I always seek God's help and guidance	4.81	0.439	Strongly Agree
I put God first before anything else	4.68	0.575	Strongly Agree
I find my inner peace when talking to God	4.78	0.473	Strongly Agree
I read religious/spiritual books to regain my spiritual self	4.40	0.708	Agree
I dwell at the place of quietness and peace to regain my soul	4.50	0.652	Strongly Agree
I pray to God for all the blessings I receive	4.80	0.461	Strongly Agree
I do hope that things will get better in the help of God	4.84	0.430	Strongly Agree
I do hope that things will get better in the help of God	4.84	0.430	Strongly Agree
I consider myself to be committed in my religious learning	4.53	0.622	Strongly Agree
I attend religious services or ceremonies in order to gain myself spiritually	4.35	0.743	Agree
I can talk with others about my fears and worries	4.12	0.880	Agree
I allowed myself to experience distressing emotions	4.19	0.760	Agree
I can plunge into the beauty of nature when I am sad	4.47	0.612	Agree
I am grateful for being complete and safe	4.72	0.514	Strongly Agree
I actively participate in religious connection and work to reduce my stress leve	4.41	0.727	Agree
I spend quality times with my families to rejoice spiritually	4.44	0.687	Agree
I encourage myself to be actively curious and interested even in a simple thing	4.49	0.680	Agree
I can participate in a religious ceremony (i.e., services)	4.42	0.729	Agree
I receive more support spiritually from my family	4.48	0.707	Agree
Overall	4.57	0.383	Strongly Agree

Table above shows the mean and standard deviation of the ABSS students level of agreement in terms of spiritual self-manifestation.

Result shows that the ABSS students level of agreement on spiritual self-manifestation have 4.57 mean which is interpreted as strongly agree. This result is evident in their high rating on item no. 1, 2, 7, 12 and 13. In giving high ratings on these items it implies that the AB Social Science students do really have no doubt that God exists and that God knows when they needed Him. With these belief they are always seeking God's help and guidance especially in times of crisis and when things are not going easy and secure like the pandemic. And so the AB Social Science students see to it to always pray to God for all the blessings they receive and are also very hopeful that things will get better in the help of God. On the other hand, the lowest rating from the ABSS students was in item 16 which states I can talk with others about my fears and worries with a mean of 4.12 and standard deviation of 0.880 and interpreted as agree. This simply means that they are not that open to others about their fears and worries as they are confident that by simply believing in God is a strong act of manifesting their spirituality and that it is good enough.

This is supported by the study of Vishkin et al., 2016, & Ramsay et al., 2019 which says that people who experience more connection with and direction from a higher power, that is, people who show high religious and spiritual involvement, tend to give a more positive appraisal of their lives. The sense of being in connection with a higher power, with others, and, in general, with life represents an effective way to maintain a positive evaluation of one's life, despite all the possible negative circumstances that one may encounter. Furthermore, Kor et al., (2019), added that among adolescents show spirituality is stable over time and contribute to better subjective well-being. It may also be considered to be a fundamental character strength and a crucial factor of positive development. Thus, spirituality may as well strengthen psychological well-being.

Significant Difference among the Respondent's Demographic Profile and Spiritual Self Manifestation

The table 3 shows the significant difference among the demographic profile of the ABSS students in terms of their level of agreement.

As to sex, Mann-Whitney U Test at 5% level of significance, a p-value of 0.496 indicates that the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. It can be concluded that there is no significant difference on the level of agreement for the manifestation of spiritual self of male and female ABSS students.

The finding of study agrees with what Bas (2013) stated that there was no significant difference between spiritual well-being scores of

female and male university students which may suggest a positive result in terms of the level of well being.

Table 3. How respondents differ in spiritual self manifestation and demographic profile (n = 162)

Demographic Profile	Test	Computed Value	P-value	Decision	Interpretation
Sex	Mann-Whitney	2,737.50	0.496	Failed to Reject Ho	Not significant
Age	Kruskal-Wallis	0.199	0.978	Failed to Reject Ho	Not significant
Year level	Kruskal-Wallis	12.298	0.006	Reject Ho	Significant
Family Monthly income	Kruskal-Wallis	0.427	0.808	Failed to Reject Ho	Not significant

On the other hand, using the Kruskal-Wallis test with the age of the respondents at 5% level of significance and a p-value of 0.978, signifies that the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. This suggests that there is no significant difference on the level of agreement for the manifestation of spiritual self of ABSS students with different ages.

The finding disagrees with the study of Zimmer et al. (2016) which indicated medium to high correlations between age and spirituality. This might be due to the small age difference between the subjects (students between 18 and 30 years of age). It is possible that with the simultaneous examinations of adolescents, students, and middle-aged people these differences would be significant.

While using the Kruskal-Wallis test with the respondents year level at 5% level of significance and a p-value of 0.006, signifies that the null hypothesis can be rejected. There is a significant difference on the level of agreement for the manifestation of spiritual self of ABSS students from different year level. Further analysis, shows that there is a significant difference on the level of agreement for the manifestation of spiritual self of 2nd year and 3rd year ABSS students. 3rd year ABSS students has the highest level of agreement while the 2nd year ABSS students level of agreement has the lowest.

The findings of the study assert with what Arnett, (2014) & Yeager et. al.,(2016) stated that aspects of spirituality continue to be associated with important outcome during students' 1st and 2nd year of college among the majority of students for whom spirituality/self-manifestation or religion is a part of their life.

Lastly, as to family monthly income, the Kruskal-Wallis test at 5% level of significance, a p-value of 0.808 signifies that the null hypothesis cannot be rejected. This implies that there is no significant difference on the level of agreement for the manifestation of spiritual self of ABSS students with different family monthly income.

Surana and Lomas (2014) found that people who overemphasize money nor family income not only exhibit more worldly but also lower levels of spiritual well-being in the transcendental domain.

Conclusions

Based on the results obtained in the study, the researchers concluded that the spiritual-self manifestation among students of Bachelor of Arts in Social Science at Central Philippines State University have a sense of connection to something higher than themselves. Valuing the meaning of their lives and the truth about the universe to cope up challenges in life, and experiences of well-being compassionately. Manifestation of students benefits literally every area of one's life because it empowers to become the very best version of life that exists, embody every individual most want to become, and help to unlock the infinite potential reflections of life to create the purpose of it in this ever-changing world. Furthermore, that most of the ABSS students have a strong level of agreement which considered students responses clear thoughts in their spiritual well-being, they expose their abilities with purpose, harmony and great balance in whatever challenges they are facing. Students connect compassionately and dedicated to risk lives with meaning and effective way to maintain positive value of one's life to face the challenges of the world.

Rooting from the findings and conclusion, the researchers strongly recommend that, the OSSA be informed with the result. Generally, there is a need for students to actively participate in different affairs, programs, and activities offered by the school and the college via online platforms or etc., striving to become more skillful, competent, and explore themselves through arts, music, nature, or studying great people or connect to something larger than themselves to level up authentic-self. This is best achieved if coordinated properly with the Office of Student Affairs and Services. Also, religious organization shall be encouraged. Given that the respondents is facing challenges manifestations of their spiritual self could be best promoted with the help of religious organizations where they could freely exercise their religious beliefs and practices. Lastly, another study of the similar objectives shall be conducted in the future. Building community of strong and resilient students in school is necessary so there is a need to know deeper their spirituality and well-being so as to properly guide them in times of hardships and crisis in life.

References

- ABS-CBN News (2020) CHED: COVID-19 pandemic slows down distribution of tertiary education subsidies. <https://www.google.com/url?sa=t&source=web&rct=j&url=https://news.abs-cbn.com/amp/news/08/29/20/>
- Alda, R. (2022). Lived Experience of Student-scholars under the Expanded Students Grants-in-Aid Program for Poverty Alleviation. <https://scholar.google.com>. American Psychological Association (2022). Pride. <https://dictionary.apa.org/pride>
- Asuncion, E. J. V., & Tullao Jr, T. S. (2018). Evaluation of Unified Student Financial Assistance System in Tertiary Education

(UniFAST) in Addressing Capital Market Imperfection in the Philippines. Working Paper Series 2018-02-049, Manila, Philippines: Angelo King Institute for Economic and Business Studies, De La Salle University. <https://www.dlsu-aki.com/uploads/1/0/2/2/102266760/complete.2018-02-049.pdf>

Capinig, et.al. (2023). The Quality of Life and Experiences of Tertiary Education Subsidy (TES) Grantees. *Psychology and Education: A Multidisciplinary Journal*. 2023 Volume: 7, Pages: 239-246, Document ID: 2022PEMJ543, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7657596

Fuentes, H. (2021) "Transitional Experiences of Tertiary Education Subsidy Grantees: A Qualitative Study." *EPRA International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research (IJMR)* 7, no. 10 (2021): 1-1. <https://scholar.google.com/scholar>

Lim, M. A., Lomer, S., & Millora, C. (2018). Universal access to quality tertiary education in the Philippines. *International Higher Education*, 94, 19-21. [https://www.research.manchester.ac.uk/portal/en/publications/universal-access-to-quality-tertiary-education-in-the-philippines\(6b297961-56f4-45dc-a3c9-61f0f2cd2284\).html](https://www.research.manchester.ac.uk/portal/en/publications/universal-access-to-quality-tertiary-education-in-the-philippines(6b297961-56f4-45dc-a3c9-61f0f2cd2284).html)

Lusardi, et.al. (2014). The Economic Importance of Financial Literacy: Theory and Evidence. *J Econ Lit.* 2014 Mar;52(1):5-44. doi: 10.1257/jel.52.1.5. PMID: 28579637; PMCID: PMC5450829.

Purigay, G. (2020). Assessment on the Implementation of Unified Student Financial Assistance System for Tertiary Education (UniFAST): Basis for a Proposed Action. <https://al-kindipublisher.com>

Republic Act 10931. Universal Access to Quality Tertiary Education Act. August 3, 2017. Philippine Law. Republic of the Philippines

Republic Act 10687. Unified Student Financial Assistance System for Tertiary Education or UniFAST. IRR.

Sustainable Development Goal (SDG) Agenda 21. Chapter 3: Combatting Poverty

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Lycel L. Pacheco

Central Philippines State University – Philippines

Zarena V. Pacheco

Central Philippines State University – Philippines

Lovelyn J. Palata

Central Philippines State University – Philippines

Girlie M. Villanueva

Central Philippines State University – Philippines